

Agronomic characteristics

Ratooning ability of some photoperiod-sensitive rices

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Ten photoperiod-sensitive deepwater and wetland rice varieties and variety IR36 were field-tested at Chinsurah to determine ratooning ability.

Pregerminated seeds were sown 14 November 1981 and transplanted 10 January 1982. Each variety was harvested the end of May. Plants were cut to 8 cm and 12 cm. Ratooning ability was scored 15 days after cutting. Plants with new tillers were considered to have ratooning ability.

Differences in ratooning ability were significant at the 1% level. Photoperiod-sensitive varieties, except Kumargorie, scored higher than IR36, highest ratooning

Ratooning ability of some rice varieties, Chinsurah, India.

Variety	Percent of hills with ratoons		
	8 cm	12 cm	Mean
SR26B	97	97	97
NC1263	92	96	94
NC365	94	92	93
Achra 108/1	97	88	93
Tillakachari	96	85	91
Bhasamanik	94	87	91
Bansmoti aman	88	89	89
Latisail	76	85	81
FR13A	86	76	81
Kumargore	71	52	62
IR36	61	61	61
Mean	87	83	
C.D. at 5%	27	28	
Pooled variety MS with 10 df	587.25*** ^a		
Pooled cutting height MS with 1 df	200.0*		
Pooled variety cutting height MS with 10 df	45.67		
Pooled error MS with 21 df	35.64		

^aTwo asterisks indicate significance at 1% level.

ing variety was SR26B (97%), followed by NC1263 (94%), Achra 108/1 (93%), NC 365 (93%), Tillakachari (91%), and

Bhasamanik (91%) (see table). Cutting height did not significantly affect ratooning ability. ✎

Disease resistance

Rice grassy stunt disease in Kerala, India

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Rice grassy stunt (GSV) is transmitted by brown planthopper (BPH). A GSV epidemic occurred in the Kuttanad tract of Kerala during punja (December-March) 1972-73.

GSV incidence in Kerala remained low until 1980 when incidence severely damaged the Kuttanad rice crop immediately following a BPH attack. In 1981 punja GSV was observed in varieties grown for the screening trial at RRS. Moncompu. Infected plants were pale green, had erect leaves with excessive tillering and stunting, and failed to flower.

The disease was severe in varieties

Aswathy, Sabari, Suriya, Sathya, Supriya, IR22, Kannaki, Jaya, TN1, ADT31, IR2058-78-1-3, and IRBN43, 48, 122, 484, and 511.

No GSV was observed on IR20, TKM9, TKM6, TKM5, Jyothy, Rohini, Triveni, Bharathy, MO 5, IR26, and IRBN46, 47, 51, 53, 54, 188, 190, 450, and 486. ✎

Incidence of kernel smut in wetland rice varieties

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Seeds of 31 varieties were examined for kernel smut infection. Sample seed lots were taken by gathering handfuls of seed and mixing. Lots of 50 g each were

examined for black pustules or streaks bursting through the glumes.

Only Bd 8 showed greater than 1% infection (see table). Six varieties showed no infection. ✎

Rice varieties showing different percentages of kernel smut.

Variety	Smutted grains (%)
Bd 8	1.9
HR 12	0.8
JR 15-552, Madhuri, Ratna, Phalguna, R115-2597, JR 16-15-1-1	0.5-0.6
Kranti, Pragati, Bd 47, RP 9-4, R115-355, Bangoli 6, R 8-2535, R 22-252, JRM 3-1-6	0.2-0.4
R 35-2752, Bd 2, Jaya, R 2384, Bapatla 1235, Surekha, Bangoli 5, CRM 13-3241	0.04-0.1
Pankaj, Mahsuri, Jagriti, Garima, Pate1 85, Safri 17	0.0